

From Scandal to Reform: Approaches to Research Integrity at a Turning Point.

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Felicitas Hesselmann, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies,
hesselmann@dzhw.eu

Martin Reinhart, Robert K. Merton Center for Science Studies, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin,
martin.reinhart@hu-berlin.de

Abstract: This perspective article explores the historical evolution of scandals related to academic integrity and their implications for the relationship between science and politics. We argue that there are three distinctive waves of scandalization since the postwar era: The first wave, starting in the 1970s, led to governance measures addressing public trust issues in science funding. The 1980s and 1990s witnessed a second wave centered on research misconduct, prompting the establishment of boundary organizations such as the Office of Research Integrity. Since the 2010s, the third wave shifted focus to concerns such as Open Science and reproducibility, giving rise to a mainly intra-scientific moral entrepreneurship that unfolds not along one-time scandals anymore, but as part of a continuous crisis discourse. This current wave of reform movements is met with considerably less intra-scientific resistance than its predecessors and hence may inadvertently achieve regulatory goals surpassing previous political intentions.

Introduction

Scandals about academic integrity have a long history. Besides being interesting phenomena in their own right, these scandals can be strategic research sites to investigate the relationship between science and society over time. More specifically, the relationship between science and politics can be traced through different political agendas, different regulatory projects and different intra-academic configurations. In this article, we will sketch this outlook on scandals in a conceptual way. Our goal here is to map out a general perspective for further inquiry using strategic examples, rather than to present systematic empirical work. We will distinguish three waves of scandalization since the postwar era: Beginning in the 1970s, when public trust in science first got under pressure following a series of scandals about science funding, a first wave of governance measures was introduced to increase public accountability of research. Subsequently, in the 1980s and 1990s, a surge of high-profile research misconduct scandals lead to a second wave of governance measures and the establishment of mainly

outward-facing institutions to address misconduct, such as the Office of Research Integrity. Since the 2010s, the third wave of scandalization has shifted towards more intra-scientific issues such as Open Science, Reproducibility, and Responsible Research and Innovation that are discussed mainly in front of and between different academic groups. These discussions now revolve around the concept of a crisis as a constant mode of engagement, rather than materialize periodically around individual cases of misconduct. Perhaps paradoxically, those intra-academic discussions then lead to a further increase in regulatory and bureaucratic measures in research from within, by far surpassing the governance approaches from politics in the beginning.

Our narrative draws from a theoretical account that conceptualizes “scandal as the disruptive publicity of transgression” (Adut 2005: 213), thereby emphasizing the social reactions to a transgression and deemphasizing the transgression itself (Adut 2008, Grattet 2008). Such a constructivist approach “remind[s] us that reactions to transgressions cannot be derived from the transgressions themselves” (Adut 2005: 217) as the disclosure of a transgression requires the (autonomous) dynamic of public discourse involving a “norm audience” to become a scandal and to, possibly, have regulatory consequences (Adut 2005: 216). While Montgomery & Oliver (2009) focussed on the changes in institutional logics, our narrative is mainly interested in how the scandalization of academic misconduct informs us on the changing sets of moral entrepreneurs, receptive audiences, and regulatory affordances at different times. In the form of three (idealtypical) phases we reconstruct, for science, Adut’s general claim of a “profanation of political authority” (Adut 2005: 242) as the main enabling condition for scandals. Our account implies, that the initial chance for transgressions to become scandals was relatively low and only increased in the context of an audience that had lower expectations on the behavior of scientists. However, to fully make the argument for a profanation of scientific authority over the same timeframe would require to revisit, as a start, the literature on knowledge societies (Weingart 2001) and the Foucauldian notion of governmentality. Since this is beyond the scope of the present article, we limit ourselves to describing these three (idealtypical) phases and drawing a conclusion on the role of scandals in science.

Early Days: Peer Review as the Answer to Scandals about Public Science Funding

It should not be surprising that science can be a contentious issue in public discourse. Historically, the great successes and promises of science have led to different types of public conflicts, e.g. between science and religion over truth claims (Galileo) or between national interests getting involved in priority disputes (Newton vs. Leibniz). During the 20th century, however, the growth in public research funding and the changing role of mass media for science and politics have turned such contentious issues into scandals. With research expenditure becoming a relevant item in national budgets, science policy also became increasingly relevant, allowing politicians to distinguish themselves by intervening in science. A telling example comes from the United States, provided by Baldwin (2018), where a notable shift took place around 1970: „A growing tension between desires for scientific autonomy and public accountability in controversies over government science funding” (Baldwin 2018: 539) had minor effects before, until a scandalized controversy over peer review at the National Science Foundation sparked institutional change (see also Montgomery & Oliver 2009: 149). A small group of congressmen challenged the funding practices of the NSF by scandalizing individual research projects in the media for their, allegedly, problematic cultural and sexual politics. This conflict over the level of autonomy for the NSF vis-à-vis congressional oversight was resolved by implementing peer review as a governance mechanism at the NSF.

While the scandalization of research funding remained the exception during that time, the institutional response to it spread widely. Peer review became the de facto standard not just for research funding but also for journals and publishers who increasingly conducted external reviewing

of manuscripts. Although the practice of peer review dates back much further than that (e.g. Shapin 1995), it was only during this time that it became the gold standard for funding procedures. As implemented in regulatory processes (Jasanoff 1985) and boundary organizations (Guston 2000), peer review became the core of how scientific autonomy and public accountability were related to each other, also outside the US (Reinhart & Schendzielorz 2024). Consequently, it seemed more improbable to scandalize science by incriminating organizational actors close to politics, such as funders or universities, for mismanagement or failures in oversight, i.e. white-collar crime. Instead, what subsequently attracted much more attention and potential for scandalization were cases of scientific misconduct by individual scientists.

Misconduct Scandals and the Establishment of Boundary Organizations in the 1980s and 1990s

During the 1980s and 1990s, scandals about scientific misconduct became a new focal issue in the relationship between science and the general public. While research misconduct itself was not necessarily new, it had been considered “extremely infrequent” (Merton 1957: 651) up until this point. However, a number of high-profile misconduct cases, from William T. Summerlin to Stephen Breuning, threatened to severely undermine public trust in science. What sparked public outrage was not (just) the deviant behavior of individual scientists, but the unsatisfactory way research institutions addressed and investigated those cases (LaFollette 1994: 264). These developments culminated in a series of Hearings in the US Congress from 1981 onwards (see also LaFollette 2000: 213), which ultimately resulted in establishing the Office of Research Integrity (ORI) in 1992 (Rhoades 2000). This general dynamic – a surge in misconduct scandals prompting political action and leading to the establishment of boundary organizations (Guston 2000) – could be observed in the 1990s and early 2000s across different countries, such as the Danish Committees on Scientific Dishonesty (UUVU) in 1992, the Ombudsman for German Science in 1998 (van Bargaen 2013), or the Dutch Landelijk Orgaan Wetenschappelijke Integriteit (LOWI) in 2003. In Korea, the Hwang affair similarly led to new misconduct regulations in 2007, although no oversight body was established here to protect academic freedom (Kim and Park 2013).

With those national oversight bodies typically also came regulatory measures at the level of research institutions, such as formal misconduct policies, research integrity officers, or sanctions for research misconduct. At first sight, it may thus seem as if this surge in misconduct scandals led to a tighter regulation of research by politics. However, these measures were met with significant resistance from within the academic community. Right from the start, academics voiced stern resistance to government regulation, which was seen as an undue influence and a threat to academic freedom (e.g. LaFollette 2000: 213, Kim and Park 2013). Institutions also only reluctantly took action and often limited their support for regulatory measures to the absolute minimum. As a result, institutional reactions to research misconduct remained highly inconsistent, with informal and often quite erratic investigative procedures (Horbach et al. 2018), producing unforeseeable outcomes, and often ending without any clear verdicts (Hesselmann & Reinhart 2021). The institutions and measures against research misconduct that resulted from a political push for more regulation of research in the wake of misconduct scandals thus were mainly outside facing instances of window-dressing that yielded little actual regulatory effect. Research practice remained largely unfazed by the rare, albeit severe, sanctions meted out in misconduct cases. Through those rather performative measures, science was then able to preserve a high degree of independence from governmental regulation.

Irreproducibility and the Current Scientific Reform Movements

While scandals about research misconduct did not vanish, over the years, the discourse around misconduct changed again. Beginning in the early 2010s, attention shifted from a moral outrage about misconduct towards a discussion of related but more benign concepts such as Research Integrity (e.g. Titus et al. 2008; Resnik & Shamoo 2011), Responsible Research and Innovation (e.g. von Schomberg 2012), Open Science (Nosek et al. 2015), and Reproducibility (e.g. Ioannidis 2005; Makel, Plucker & Hegarty 2012). Deviant behavior in research is now predominantly addressed under the concept of Questionable Research Practices (QRPs, e.g. John, Loewenstein & Prelec 2012, Schneider et al. 2023), denoting a variety of practices that are widespread and do not strictly violate academic norms, but that are still considered harmful to research. With this shift, discussions then center around either desirable (research integrity) or at least morally more neutral aspects (QRPs), that additionally concern (supposedly) widespread behaviors instead of focusing on a few extreme and scandalous cases.

Together, these topics form the heart of a new wave of Scientific Reform movements (Nelson et al. 2021, Penders 2022). These movements rally for a variety of measures in research practice, including to publish in Open Access journals and on preprint servers, to make data publicly available, to report methods in a more transparent (and standardized) fashion, or to preregister studies. Academic credibility and public trust feature as prominent concerns within this discourse (e.g. Ioannidis 2012; Anvari & Lakens 2019), however, this concern is no longer raised by the general public or by politics themselves. Instead, the new reform movements are predominantly intra-academic and rely heavily on digital means of communication such as blogs, social media, or platforms like PubPeer. There, discussions are often highly technical and require in-depth knowledge of, both, specific research methods and the research system more broadly. Moreover, they revolve around mundane research practices, such as the keeping of lab notebooks or the use of statistics, which in contrast to the sometimes quite thrilling stories of research fraud have little allure to the general public.

While those newer concepts are still discussed with a strong sense of urgency, they do not unfold around scandals, but rather represent a constant mode of engagement—a crisis. Fueled by a constant stream of online communication (Maasen & Sutter 2016, Hendriks & Reinhart 2020, Reinhart 2022), this shift enables more systemic critiques that bring into view the underlying structures and conditions of the current research system, e.g. incentives and reward systems, power structures, and the academic attention economy, on the one hand. On the other hand, this systemic perspective also creates a constant and reliable need for attention and intervention, allowing researchers to build a career out of addressing these issues. These scientific reform movements then mainly unfold in the form of discursive struggles and struggles for influence and power between different academic groups and fields, rather than as conflicts between science and politics. In this current setting, the scandalous mode of engaging with academic transgressions has given way to a more continuous, less spectacular mode that sees individual cases of misconduct not as extraordinary events requiring immediate action (e.g. punishment), but as symptoms of systematic issues requiring long term cultural change, i.e. reform. If that is the case, investigating academic misconduct with concepts and theories that focus on the temporary and exceptional, such as scandal, may become less adequate for the phenomenon at hand.

Consequences: The Regulatory Project Comes Full Circle

We sketched a historical development of how scientific misconduct and its scandalization are involved in how science is governed. We provided three quite distinct snapshots across the last 70 years: Scandals, in the first phase, were initiated by politicians, targeted organizations (esp. for public research funding), and problematized financial oversight. In the second phase, scandals were initiated by journalists, targeted individual scientists, and exposed individual fraud within academia. Currently, scandals are invoked by an intra-scientific reform movement, addressing systemic aspects of science,

and problematizing quality assurance and reporting standards (e.g. reproducibility). The scandalization of misconduct in science began as regulatory interventions for political power, morphed into media hypervisibility for newspaper sales, and has now turned into moral entrepreneurship for intra-scientific competition between researchers and disciplines.

Each phase draws from different modes of governance with the first being distinctly political, the second mostly symbolic, and the third, still in the making, bureaucratic. The current reform movement aims strongly at implementing standards and bureaucratic procedures not just for academic organizations but for the research work of individual scientists (Penders 2022). Even though this may look very different from the regulatory project of the first phase, its effects may fulfill the original political intentions. As long as conflicts around misconduct were seen as an external pressure (from politics or media), they met considerable resistance from within academia. Such resistance seems more difficult to organize and uphold when the pressure comes from other scientists, i.e. from within. In effect, the current reform movement may prove more effective in regulating and formalizing the research process, even surpassing any original regulatory intentions by politics from the 1970s. As can already be seen, this regulatory project from within has opened the door for allies in politics and media to join the movement and push for change in academic culture according to their (political) preferences.

One of the main enabling conditions for this situation is the change in how academic misconduct is scandalized in public discourse driven by social media in front of an (academic) audience now accustomed to a long line of major and minor cases of academic transgressions. When that audience expects that “most published research findings are false” (Voldemort 2005) individual transgressions are normalized to the point that moral entrepreneurs have little success in leveraging them as scandals to further a regulatory agenda. The shift of terminology around academic misconduct towards “research integrity” and “responsible research and innovation” indicates that scandalization of academic misconduct may have lost power in mobilizing outrage from the public and, thus, as an important driver of social change in academia. Irrespective of whether its substitute is a view of social problems in academia that relies on notions from more bureaucratic or managerial or techno-solutionist understandings, we are left with a theoretical problem: What comes after scandal? Adut’s theory claims that scandals bring about more scandals when institutions such as politics or science are faced with diminishing reputation, which seems to imply a self-reinforcing social process of ever more scandals and more profanation (see also Hesselmann & Reinhart 2021). How such a process either limits itself, or turns around, or changes into something else would be a pressing issue for further work on a theory of scandal and would help us better understand the current situation at the nexus of science, politics, and its publics.

References

Adut, Ari (2005) ‘A Theory of Scandal: Victorians, Homosexuality, and the Fall of Oscar Wilde’, *American Journal of Sociology*, 111(1), pp. 213–248. <https://doi.org/10.1086/428816>

Adut, Ari (2008) *On scandal: moral disturbances in society, politics, and art*. Cambridge; New York: Cambridge University Press. <http://archive.org/details/onscandalmoraldi0000adut>

Anvari, Farid, and Daniël Lakens, (2018) The replicability crisis and public trust in psychological science, *Comprehensive Results in Social Psychology*, 3:3, 266–286, [10.1080/23743603.2019.1684822](https://doi.org/10.1080/23743603.2019.1684822)

Baldwin, Melinda. “Scientific Autonomy, Public Accountability, and the Rise of ‘Peer Review’ in the Cold War United States.” *Isis*, vol. 109, no. 3, 2018, pp. 538–58, <https://doi.org/10.1086/700070>.

Grattet, Ryken (2011) ‘Societal Reactions to Deviance’, *Annual Review of Sociology*, 37, pp. 185–204.

- Guston, David H. (2000) *Between Politics and Science: Assuring the Integrity and Productivity of Research*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hendriks, Barbara and Reinhart, Martin (2020) 'Science Blogs as Critique — Building Public Identities in the Field of Translational Research', *Science & Technology Studies*, 33(3), pp. 19–38. <https://doi.org/10.23987/sts.75153>.
- Hesselmann, Felicitas, and Martin Reinhart. "Cycles of Invisibility: The Limits of Transparency in Dealing with Scientific Misconduct." *Social Studies of Science*, vol. 51, no. 3, 2021, pp. 414–38, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312720975201>.
- Horbach, Serge P. J. M., et al. "Organisational Responses to Alleged Scientific Misconduct: Sensemaking, Sensegiving, and Sensehiding." *Science and Public Policy*, vol. 46, no. 3, June 2019, pp. 415–29, <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scy068>.
- Ioannidis, John P. A. "Why Science Is Not Necessarily Self-Correcting." *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, vol. 7, no. 6, 2012, pp. 645–54, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612464056>.
- Jasanoff, Sheila. "Peer Review in the Regulatory Process." *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, vol. 10, no. 3, 1985, pp. 20–32, <https://doi.org/10.1177/016224398501000303>.
- John, Leslie K., et al. "Measuring the Prevalence of Questionable Research Practices With Incentives for Truth Telling." *Psychological Science*, vol. 23, no. 5, 2012, pp. 524–32, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797611430953>.
- Kim, Jongyoung, and Kibeom Park. "Ethical Modernization: Research Misconduct and Research Ethics Reforms in Korea Following the Hwang Affair." *Science and Engineering Ethics*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2013, pp. 355–80, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-011-9341-8>.
- LaFollette, M. "The Evolution of the 'Scientific Misconduct' Issue: An Historical Overview (44535C)." *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*, vol. 224, no. 4, 2000, pp. 211–15, <https://doi.org/10.1177/153537020022400405>.
- LaFollette, Marcel C. "The Politics of Research Misconduct: Congressional Oversight, Universities, and Science." *The Journal of Higher Education*, vol. 65, no. 3, 1994, p. 261, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2943967>.
- Maasen, Sabine and Sutter, Barbara (2016) 'Dezentraler Panoptismus', *Geschichte und Gesellschaft*, 42(1), pp. 175–194.
- Makel, Matthew C., et al. "Replications in Psychology Research: How Often Do They Really Occur?" *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, vol. 7, no. 6, 2012, pp. 537–42, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612460688>.
- Merton, Robert K. "Priorities in Scientific Discovery: A Chapter in the Sociology of Science." *American Sociological Review*, vol. 22, no. 6, 1957, p. 635, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2089193>.
- Montgomery, K. and Oliver, A.L. (2009) 'Shifts in Guidelines for Ethical Scientific Conduct: How Public and Private Organizations Create and Change Norms of Research Integrity1', *Social Studies of Science*, 39(1), pp. 137–155. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312708097659>.
- Nelson NC, Ichikawa K, Chung J, Malik MM (2021) Mapping the discursive dimensions of the reproducibility crisis: A mixed methods analysis. *PLOS ONE* 16(7): e0254090. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254090>

Nosek, B. A., et al. "Promoting an Open Research Culture." *Science*, vol. 348, no. 6242, June 2015, pp. 1422–25, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aab2374>.

Penders, Bart. "Process and Bureaucracy: Scientific Reform as Civilisation." *Bulletin of Science, Technology & Society*, vol. 42, no. 4, 2022, pp. 107–16, <https://doi.org/10.1177/02704676221126388>.

Reinhart, Martin (2022) "Open Science as an Engine of Anxiety: How Scientists Promote and Defend the Visibility of Their Digital Selves, while Becoming Fatalistic about Academic Careers", in: Brighenti, Andrea Mubi "The New Politics of Visibility", Intellect Books, S. 175-200.

Resnik, David B., and Adil E. Shamoo. "The Singapore Statement on Research Integrity." *Accountability in Research*, vol. 18, no. 2, Mar. 2011, pp. 71–75, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2011.557296>.

Rhoades, Lawrence & Gorski, A. (2000). *Scientific misconduct: An international perspective*. *Science and Engineering Ethics* 6 (1):5-10.

Schneider, Jesper W., Nick Allum, Jens P. Andersen, Michael Bang Petersen, Niels Mejlgaard, and Robert Zachariae. 2023. "Is Something Rotten in the State of Denmark? Cross-national Evidence for Widespread Involvement but Not Systematic Use of Questionable Research Practices Across All Fields of Research." *MetaArXiv*. September 13. doi:10.31222/osf.io/r6j3z.

Shapin, S. (1995). *A social history of truth: Civility and science in seventeenth-century England*. University of Chicago Press.

Titus, Sandra L., et al. "Repairing Research Integrity." *Nature*, vol. 453, no. 7198, 2008, pp. 980–82, <https://doi.org/10.1038/453980a>.

von Bargen, Joachim. "Wissenschaftliche Redlichkeit und zentrales hochschulinternes Verfahrensrecht." *JuristenZeitung*, vol. 68, no. 14, July 2013, pp. 714–23, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23467527>.

Von Schomberg, René. "Prospects for technology assessment in a framework of responsible research and innovation." *Technikfolgen abschätzen lehren*, edited by Marc Dusseldorp and Richard Beecroft, VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, 2012, pp. 39–61, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-531-93468-6_2.

Weingart, Peter (2001) *Die Stunde der Wahrheit?: Zum Verhältnis der Wissenschaft zu Politik, Wirtschaft und Medien in der Wissensgesellschaft*. Weilerswist: Velbrück Wissenschaft.